

Livelihoods for Ethnic Minority Households in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam

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Abstract:

Theories and frameworks of livelihoods by scholars and DIFD were defined. Furthermore, the study finds out five factors of the framework of livelihood as external context, institutional and policy process, livelihood assets, livelihood strategies, and livelihood outcomes. Typical framework on 1) Scooner's sustainable rural livelihood framework source (1998), 2) DFID sustainable livelihood analysis, 3) Sustainable livelihood framework IFAD (2003) was introduced. DFID framework was used to analyze livelihood analytical frameworks of ethnic minorities in the study area of Thai Nguyen province. Main factors affecting the livelihood of ethnic minority households, such as policy and government program, shocks and risk, education and training, characteristics of ethnic minority groups, and development program aid.

Keywords: Livelihoods, Ethnic Minority

1. Introduction

Thai Nguyen is a mountainous area. There are 8 districts, 1 city, 164 communes, wards and towns. The population is over 637 thousand people, which 25 different ethnic minority groups accounts for 64.1%. The large area of agricultural, forestry land, many climate sub- regions together with rich natural mineral resource is a great potential for Thai Nguyen in the process of development of (Thai Nguyen Statistic Department, 2017).

Over the past few years, Thai Nguyen Province has received support from many projects funded by Vietnamese government, other agencies and NGOs. Particularly from 2009 up to now, ODA donors and non-governmental organizations have invested a total capital of 154 million USD in Thai Nguyen for rural infrastructure development, urban infrastructure, economy development linked to sustainable poverty reduction, environmental protection and human resource development. Together with international donor funded projects on poverty reduction, programs, projects using state budget such as NTP on NRD, Program 135, Program 30a, NTP on fresh water and rural sanitation, National Program on education and training implemented in the province have brought positive changes. The poverty rate decreased rapidly at average of 5% per year.

In the process of international integration, expansion of border trade and along with the government's support policies, Thai Nguyen has had a strong development pace in recent years and achieved various significant successes in all aspects. Economic growth for the period 2010 - 2015 reached an average rate of over 14%. Rural infrastructure has been significantly improved. The quality of education has been enhanced and enrollment ratio has been maintained. Thai Nguyen People's health care has been improved as well as the guarantee of social security. In addition, public administration reform has achieved positive results. The business environment of the province has been highly appreciated by enterprises.

However, Thai Nguyen still faces many difficulties and challenges, such as unfavorable weather including natural disasters like hail, flash flood, and snow in the mountainous districts like Muong Khuong, Bac Ha, Si Ma Cai, Sa Pa and Bat Xat, which causes great damages to people and materials. The poverty rate has declined, but it still remains high, especially among ethnic minority households. The high poverty rate is still prevailing in some localities in the province, majorly in 6 districts such as Bac Ha (28.5%), Simacai (29.5%), Muong Khuong (31.3%), Sapa (25.3%), Van Ban (22.2%), and Bat Xat (21.6%). Most ethnic minority groups are involved in agricultural production. They grow maize as their main food crop and raise buffalo, cows, goats and

February 28, 2021

pigs. Few ethnic minority members are involved in other activities (services, government, etc.). The livelihoods are not divers. The production is mainly for self- sufficiency and lack of commodity products, so the income level of households is lower than non-ethnic minority households. The poor in these regions are struggling to raise their livelihood and living standards, accessing new technologies, credit, market, but particularly being vulnerable to natural disasters leads to fragile livelihood.

2. Literature review

2.1. Basic theory

A household is a unit of society consisting of one or more of a group of people living and eating together (demographics). For households with two or more members, household members may or may not have general income or general income fund. Households are not consistent with a concept of the family; people in the household may or may not have blood relations, nurture or marriage, or both.

Households whose members jointly contribute their labor and common property for general economic cooperation in agricultural, forestry or fishery production or in a number of other business domains prescribed by law, being owners in such civil relations.

“Ethnic minority is a group of people of a particular race or nationality living in a country or area where most people are from a different race or nationality” (Oxford University, 2014)

In the 1960s, the government of Vietnam had paid attention to the identification of ethnic minorities. Under the government requirement, National Program of Ethnic Classification was first conducted by Vietnamese ethnologists by Institute of Ethnology. They defined an ethnic group (dan toc) as a stable or relatively stable group of people formed over a historical period with common territorial ties, economic activities, and cultural characteristics. And the official academic definition of an “ethnicity” is “a stable community, formed over a historical period, involving relationships of identity in regard to language, habitat, socioeconomic activities, and cultural characteristics – a community whose members are also conscious of their shared ethnic identity, on the basis of foregoing relations”. The Vietnamese population, therefore, was classified into 54 official ethnic groups, of which the Kinh is the vast majority and the remaining consists of 53 other groups, officially called the ethnic minorities (dan toc thieu so, dan toc it nguoi) (Dang, 1998).

Combining the two concepts above, ethnic minority households are understood to be household with members are ethnic minorities. In the case of marriage between different ethnic groups, it is generally understood that household head is an ethnic minority.

Vietnam is a unified nation which is home to 54 ethnic groups (53 groups of ethnic minorities, accounting for 14% of the total population) with some following basic traits:

i) They are mainly living in mountainous, remote and border areas

Non-Chinese minority people of Vietnam are mostly highlanders who live in relative independence and follow their own traditional customs and culture. They are classified as either sedentary or nomadic. The sedentary groups, the more numerous of the two kinds, are engaged mainly in the cultivation of wet rice and industrial crops; the nomadic groups, in slash- and-burn farming where forested land is cleared for a brief period of cultivation and then abandoned. Both groups inhabit in the same four major areas: the northern Chinese border region and the uplands adjacent to the Red River Delta, the northwestern border region adjoining Laos and China, the Central Highlands and the area along the Truong Son, and parts of the Mekong River Delta and the central coastal strip.

ii) Ethnic minorities live together with others. Each has a different level of socio- economic development, but there is no separate territorial division and social regime among groups

February 28, 2021

The pattern of residence with many ethnic groups show the solidarity and unification of Vietnamese as a nation. In recent years, the trait is now on an increasing trend, together with the development of economy, culture and society. Nowadays, in mountainous areas, there is almost no province or district where there are only two ethnic groups, namely provinces of Lai Chau, Thai Nguyen, Yen Bai, Ha Giang, Kon Tum, Gia Lai, Dak Lak, Dak Nong, and Lam Dong ... Due to different geographical location, custom, psychology and lifestyle, the level of socio-economic development of regions and ethnic groups is uneven. Some ethnic groups have small population in remote areas, and encounter many socio- economic difficulties, such as ethnic groups of Si La, Pu Pon, Ro Mam, Brau, O Du (Ha Thi Dang Huong, 2016).

They are living in harmony. Since the country's establishment, ethnic groups have collaborated with each other to fight against natural disasters; the spirit of unity has been further promoted in the history of fighting against foreign aggressors for national liberation.

iii) Each ethnic group has its own cultural identity, creating a diverse, rich and unified Vietnamese culture

These groups are notable for their diverse cultural characteristics. Each has its own customs, habits, psychology, lifestyles and religious beliefs, which develop a unique cultural trait of each ethnic group, exist and develop in the diversity and system of the Vietnamese culture (Ha Thi Dang Huong, 2016). They are distinguished from one another not only by language but also by other cultural features, such as architectural styles, colors and shapes of dress and personal ornaments, shapes of agricultural implements, religious practices, and systems of social organization.

The number and variety of languages used by Vietnam's minorities reflect the country's ethnic complexity. Minority groups are distinguished by more than a dozen distinctive languages and numerous dialects; the origins and distribution of many of these languages have not yet been conclusively established. They can, however, be classified loosely into three major language families, which in turn can be divided into several subgroups. Eleven of the minority groups--Tay, Thai, Nung, Hmong, Muong, Cham, Khmer, Kohor, Ede, Bahnar, and Jarai--have their own writing systems.

Religious practices among highland minorities tend to be rooted in animistic beliefs. Most worship a pantheon of spirits, but a large number are Catholics or Protestants. In contrast to the Mahayana Buddhist beliefs of the majority of Vietnamese, the Khmer practice Theravada (or Hinayana) Buddhism, and the Cham subscribe to both Islam and Hindu beliefs.

iv) The residence place of ethnic minorities play a very important role in politics, economics, culture, security, national defense and foreign affairs and sustainable protection of ecological environment

They live along the borderlines in the north, west and southwest where there are many trade gateways between the country and other countries in the region and in the world. Those areas have rich and diversified resource, protective forests and specially-used for national development and sustainable ecology.

Under the current context, the mountainous area is the potential, strategic and fundamental one for the country development and protection.

v) The economy in the mountainous areas or in areas of ethnic minorities is still underdeveloped

The situation of shifting cultivation, nomadic and free migration is still occurring. Infrastructure (electricity, roads, schools, stations, services) in remote areas still faces many difficulties; and in some areas, the ecological environment continues to deteriorate (Ha Thi Dang Huong, 2016).

The proportion of poor and hungry households in ethnic minority and mountainous areas is higher than the national average rate. The gap in living standards and socio-economic development among ethnic groups and among areas is on increase. The quality and efficiency of education and training is still low. Healthcare for

February 28, 2021

ethnic minorities is encountering many difficulties. Some good cultural identities of ethnic minorities are getting lost whilst some backward practices and superstitious belief tend to develop (CEMA, 2015).

There are numerous approaches and definitions on livelihood. In the report of an Advisory Panel of the World Commission on Environment and Development, a concept of livelihoods was put forward as follows: “livelihood is defined as adequate stocks and flows of food and cash to meet basic needs”.

Chambers et al. (1992) stated that a livelihood comprises the capabilities, assets (including both physical and social capital) and activities required for a means of living. A livelihood is sustainable when it can cope with and recover from stress and shocks and manage to enhance its capabilities and assets both now and in the future, while not undermining the natural resource base.

Ellis defined livelihoods as the assets (natural, physical, human, financial and social assets), activities and opportunities to access to these assets and activities (via institutions and social relations) that jointly determine the living gained by individual or households (Ellis, 2000). The five main categories of assets include natural resource base that yields products for human survival; physical capital that refers to assets created by economic production processes such as tools and irrigation schemes; human capital referring to the education and health of the individual or population; financial capital referring to stocks of cash and access to credit; and social capital that refers to the social networks and associations that people can derive support from (Ellis, 2000).

According to the Department for International Development (DFID, 1998), livelihood could be defined as a bundle of resources and human abilities, incorporating with decisions and activities they make for their livings and realizing their targets and expectations.

A livelihood can be studied by taking into account with the changes in social, cultural and natural capital of a geographical area or it can be studied more narrowly, for example, defining livelihood as comprising income, both cash and in kind, as well as the social institutions and property rights geared to support it (Lipton et al., 1992; Ellis, 2000). This study is focusing on the latter perspective of livelihood as considering how people make a living.

Thus, this study considers a livelihood system as one in which with the support of entitlements and institutions and through natural and/or man-made processes, people’s labor and materials (input) will be converted into income and subsistence benefits (output). Again, the income would sustain people, their households and their supporting institutions to pursue a livelihood. Rural livelihoods most often involve two or more activities, depending upon people’s capabilities, assets and entitlements, markets, and availability of local resources (Kydd et al., 2001).

Although a variety of explanations are offered in the literature on livelihoods, it is a highly contested concept. Consequently, governments, organizations and individuals have adopted it according to their own understanding (Development, 1999). However, the genesis of this concept can be traced back to the work of Chambers and Conway (1992), who sought to theoretically locate sustainable livelihoods within the actor-oriented approaches to development, the framework of environmental and social sustainability and the rhetoric of poverty reduction. Chambers introduced this thinking as a response to the Brundt land Report (WCED, 1987), which had, for the first time, firmly put sustainable development on a global political agenda. In the 1992 United Nations Conference on Environment and Development (UNCED), it was conceded that sustainable livelihoods can serve as an integrating factor that allows policies to address development, sustainable resource management and poverty eradication simultaneously (Hoon et al., 1997). The 1995 World Summit for Social Development and the 1996 World Food Summit had also shared much of this analysis. Hence, the social and ecological costs of the conventional development models, the subsequent environment and development movements of the late 1980s and 1990s gave rise to the need for sustainable development paradigm. Since then, the sustainable

February 28, 2021

livelihoods perspective has an overarching discursive influence in both national and international policy circles (Shaw, 2007).

Chambers and Conway (1992) provided a definition of sustainable livelihoods, relating it to the assets that are used by the poor to withstand shocks and stresses including the three concepts of capabilities, equity and sustainability. Capabilities in this context refer to a person's or a household's ability to cope with stresses and shocks as well as to find and make use of livelihood opportunities. Assets refer to the basic physical and social capital that people have in their possession. Activities indicate the ways in which capabilities and assets are combined to achieve livelihood outcomes (Scoones, 1998). In accord, Ashley and Carney (1998) illustrated that the significance of the concept of sustainable livelihoods is borne by desire to empower capacity of people to earn income that meets their current and future economic and social needs and minimizes their vulnerability to external stresses and shocks (Ashley et al., 1999). In addition, Scoones (1998) cautioned that an inequitable access to livelihood opportunities lead to income disparity and widespread poverty coupled with environmental degradation, social unrest and political instability.

There is pertinent literature to suggest that sustainable livelihoods perspective helps to enlist objectives, scope and priorities for development, based on the core principles of people-centered, participatory and sustainable activities. Krantz (2001) applauded it as a more reasoned and holistic approach to poverty eradication and pro-poor development (Krantz, 2001), Ludi and Slater (2007) called it a distinct perspective on understanding the lived reality of people. They concurred that it can be used to analyze how interventions tackle the non-material dimensions of poverty and contribute to strengthen a household's asset portfolio, thus enhancing their livelihood options and well-being. Additionally, many of the early reviews suggested that this approach was particularly useful for: the systematic and holistic analysis of poverty; providing an informed view of development opportunities, challenges and impacts; and placing people at the center of development (Jones et al., 2010). The sustainable livelihoods approaches have also led to: improving understanding of poor people's lives; the constraints facing them, and inter-group differences; increasing inter sectoral, collaborative and interdisciplinary community development research and work; and creating increased links between micro-, meso- and macro-level considerations in poverty and development discourse (Hussein, 2002). Ellis and Biggs (2001) remarked that all these characteristics make it consistent with the bottom-up approach to development (Ellis et al., 2001). Current research on livelihood establishes basic analysis is framework for sustainable livelihood based on the level of five capitals of households including material, natural, financial, human and social capitals.

Sustainable livelihood is a livelihood strategy in which all sustainable elements are ensured. These elements are economy, environment and institutions. The sustainability of livelihood activities largely depends on many factors such as capital accessibility, human capital, social relations, and development policies. However, the sustainability of natural resources is foundation to decide the sustainability of a livelihood.

In general, a livelihood of a household and community is considered to be sustainable when:

- (i) Individuals, households, and communities can overcome shocks caused by natural disaster, diseases and economic crisis.
- (ii) They can expand their current resources without exerting negative effects on natural environment.

Livelihood improvement is an act that aims to improve livelihood outcomes in a stable and sustainable manner. These activities may be single or combination of the following activities: i) Improving livelihoods capitals: Improving access ability to these resources for ethnic minority households; Using more sustainability and effectively livelihood resources; ii) Creating or modifying livelihood activities and strategies. The diversification of livelihood activities will improve livelihood outcomes, create stability and mitigate risks; iii) Reducing the external negative factors that affect livelihood resources or livelihood outcomes;

iv) Implementing appropriate supporting policies to improve the efficiency of livelihood resources and create stable and sustainable livelihoods.

At the moment, there are many perspectives on sustainable livelihoods. Basically, the structure of sustainable livelihood analyzes an interaction of five factor groups to household livelihoods: External context, Institutional and policy process, Livelihood assets, Livelihood strategies and Livelihood outcomes;

Scoones (1998) was the first to provide an analytical framework for sustainable rural livelihoods. This framework works on such issues: the specific context (policy environment, politics, history, ecology and socio-economic conditions), combination of livelihood assets (5 different types of capital) will create the capacity to implement livelihood strategies to achieve certain livelihood outcomes. The main concerns in this framework are institutional and policy processes - which are considered as intermediaries for implementing these livelihood strategies and achieving the desired livelihood outcomes (Scoones, 1998).

- DFID's Sustainable Livelihood Framework

The DFID Sustainable Livelihoods Framework highlights a number of key components in livelihood. Firstly, the framework places people, particularly rural poor people at the center of a web of inter-related influences that affect how these people create a livelihood for themselves and their households. The closest to the people at the center of the framework are the resources and livelihood assets or livelihood capitals that they have access to and use. These can include natural resources, technologies, their skills, knowledge and capacity, their health, access to education, sources of credit, or their networks of social support. The extent of their access to these assets is strongly influenced by their vulnerability context, which takes an account of trends (for example, economic, political, and technological), shocks (for example, epidemics, natural disasters, civil strife) and seasonality (for example, prices, production, and employment opportunities). The SLF clarifies that risks are linked to rules and they affect assets, but strong assets can resist risks or can be used to influence of rules that enable risks to be managed with more certainty. Access is also influenced by the prevailing social, institutional and political environment, which affects the ways in which people combine and use their assets to achieve their goals. These are their livelihood strategies (DFID, 2001).

Livelihood strategies as defined by DFID (1998) are the range and combination of activities and choices that individuals and communities carry out in order to attain their livelihood outcomes.

Livelihood outcomes are the goals which people aspire; results of pursuing their livelihood strategies, such as increased income, reduced vulnerability, increased well-being, improved food security, and more sustainable use of natural resources. Livelihoods outcomes are important because they help an analyst to understand the results of peoples' livelihoods strategies in a particular context, including why people pursue particular strategies and what their priorities are, and how people are likely to respond to new opportunities or constraints. Assets, which people can rely upon, play a crucial role in the livelihoods framework. Those with more assets are more likely to have greater livelihood options with how to pursue their goals and reduce poverty. Traditionally, five categories of assets or capitals (i.e., human, social, natural, physical, and financial) are identified, although subsequent adaptations have added others (DFID, 2001).

Policies, institutions and processes refer to complex social, economic and political context within which people pursue their livelihood strategies. They can have a great influence on access to assets – creating them, determining access, and influencing rates of asset accumulation. These elements in the sustainable livelihoods framework cover the inter-related issues of social relations, social and political organization, governance, service delivery, social norms, policy and policy processes. These operate at global, national, regional, district and local levels. Key to understanding their impact on local livelihoods is an analysis of the operation, or absence, of links between micro, meso and macro levels (DFID, 2001).

February 28, 2021

The vulnerability context within which people pursue their livelihoods includes trends (for example, economic or resource trends), shocks (for example, conflict, economic shocks, natural shocks, etc.), and seasonal fluctuations in prices, production, health, and employment opportunities. These factors can have a direct impact on people's assets and options available to them to pursue beneficial livelihood strategies. The vulnerability context of poor people's livelihoods is usually influenced by external factors outside their direct control and is dependent on wider policies, institutions and processes. To support people in order for them to be more resilient to the negative effects of trends, shocks and seasonality, development policy-makers and practitioners can support people's access to assets and help ensure that critical policies, institutions and processes are responsive to their needs (DFID, 2001).

Below is the SLF, which shows that the way to develop sustainable livelihoods is for people to use their assets to design strategies whose outcomes build those assets, and to learn from their experience to influence rules to improve those strategies. The important role for such a framework is to help people understand pathways that need to be followed in order to improve their livelihood (LaFlamme, 2010).

Figure 1. DFID Sustainable Livelihood Analysis

Source: (DFID, 2001)

According to IFAD (2003), the sustainable livelihoods framework is described in the figure below.

Nguyen Van Suu (2010) points out that, compared to DFID's sustainable livelihood analysis framework, IFAD's livelihood analysis has some adjustments as follows:

- Rearrange the elements in the analytical framework to clarify the relationship among them.
- The new livelihood framework places the poor at the center of the figure and arranges other factors within the framework of their relationship.
- The spiritual life in the livelihood is emphasized. Factors such as sex, age, rankings, education, ethnicity, religion are put next to the poor (at the center) as factors affecting the relationship of the poor to other elements in the livelihood framework (Solesbury, 2003).

February 28, 2021

- The "personal" element is added to the livelihoods of the sustainable livelihoods framework. It is aimed to emphasize the internal force of people, which promotes and change their livelihoods.
- Factors such as institutions, culture and market are set as interactions with the central element (the poor) and sources of livelihood. The new Sustainable Livelihood Analysis Framework launched by IFAD has adequate elements and a more rigorous representation of poverty-centered factors. This is considered as a model for reference in community livelihood analysis (Culas et al., 2010).

The five principal capitals, which are important to livelihood are presented as a pentagon in the diagram below.

In order to create livelihoods, people must combine the “capital” endowments that they have access over (Scoones, 1998). These may be made up of tangible assets such as stores (for example, good stocks, and stores of value such as gold, jewelry, and cash savings), and resources (including land, water, trees, livestock, and farm equipment) as well as intangible assets, such as claims (for instance, demands and appeals which can be made for materials, moral or other practical support) and access (which is the opportunity to use a resource and service or to obtain information, material, technology, employment, food or income) (Chambers et al., 1992; Scoones, 1998).

The shape of the pentagon can be used to show schematic variation in people’s access to assets. The idea is that the center point of the pentagon, where all lines meet, represents zero access to assets while the outer perimeter represents maximum access to assets. On this basis, different shaped pentagons can be drawn for different communities or social groups within communities.

It is important to note that a single physical capital can generate multiple benefits. If someone has secure access to land (natural capital), they may also be well-endowed with financial capital, as they are able to use the land not only for direct productive activities but also as collateral for loans. Similarly, livestock may generate social capital (prestige and connectedness to the community) for owners while at the same time being used as productive physical capital (think of animal traction) and remaining, in itself, as natural capital. In order to develop an understanding of these complex relationships, it is necessary to look beyond assets themselves, to think about prevailing cultural practices and the types of structures and processes that ‘transform’ assets into livelihood outcomes. Pentagons will be useful as a focus point for a debate about every suitable points on how these will serve needs of different social groups and how they will likely become trade-offs between different assets. At general level, there is no suggestion that we can – or should – quantify all assets, let alone develop some kind of common currency that allows direct comparison between assets. This does not, of course, rule out the development of specific, quantifiable indicators of assets where these are thought to be useful.

Asset endowments are constantly changing. Therefore, pentagons are constantly shifting as well. A three-dimensional framework, with the third dimension representing time, would enable this change to be visualized. In contrast, two dimensional frameworks do not. However, it is imperative to incorporate the time dimension into any analysis of assets. Information should be gathered on trends in overall asset availability (e.g. if societies fragment, the overall ‘stock’ of social capital might decline), as well as on which groups are accumulating assets, which are losing and why. Where processes of ‘social exclusion’ are at work, those who are already poorly endowed with assets may well be becoming gradually, but notably, more marginalized.

By exploiting livelihood capitals, livelihood activities of ethnic minority households will be performed. Based on strengths and opportunities from livelihood resources, households will have appropriate livelihoods activities. Livelihood activities include agricultural production, handicraft industry and service activities. Depending on the characteristics and resources of the household, the number of livelihood activities will vary. Livelihood activities also vary by sub- ecological region and different ethnic minority groups.

February 28, 2021

Each household, with their own resources, will have different livelihood strategies. Livelihood strategies can be a way for households to reduce the risks and negative externalities. Livelihood strategies can be the current strategy of household or strategy in the future.

The results of this analysis help to find appropriate and potential livelihood models for ethnic minority households. This is the basis for proposing solutions to improve livelihoods of ethnic minority households.

Livelihood outcomes are the achievements or outputs of Livelihood Strategies. Once again, the important idea associated with this component of the framework is that we, as outsiders, investigate, observe and listen, rather than jumping to conclusions or making hasty judgments about the exact nature of the outcomes that people pursue. In particular, we should not assume that people are entirely dedicated to maximizing their income. Instead, we should recognize and seek to understand the richness of potential livelihood goals. This, in turn, will help us to understand people's priorities, why they do what they do, and where the major constraints lie (DFID, 2001). The livelihood outcomes that appear in the generic framework are effectively categorized, introducing to make this section of the framework more manageable. Each one may or may not be relevant in any given situation – this can only be established through participatory enquiry.

(i) **More income:** Although income measures of poverty have been much criticized, people certainly continue to seek a simple increase in net returns to the activities they undertake and overall increases in the amount of money coming into the household (or their own pocket). Increased income also relates to the idea of the economic sustainability of livelihoods.

(ii) **Increased well-being:** In addition to income and things that money can be purchased, people value nonmaterial goods. Their sense of well-being is affected by numerous factors, possibly including: their self-esteem, sense of control and inclusion, physical security of household members, their health status, access to services, political enfranchisement, maintenance of their cultural heritage, etc.

(iii) **Reduced vulnerability:** Poor people are often forced to live precariously, with no cushion against the adverse effects of the vulnerability context. For such people, reducing their vulnerability to the downside and increasing the overall social sustainability of their livelihoods may well take precedence over seeking to maximize the upside.

(iv) **Improved food security:** Food insecurity is a core dimension of vulnerability. It appears as a separate category in the framework in order to emphasize its fundamental importance, and because this helps to locate the activities of those governments and donors that focus on food security. It is also worth noting that participatory poverty assessments have shown hunger and dietary inadequacy to be a distinct dimension of deprivation.

(v) **More sustainable use of the natural resource base:** Environmental sustainability, or sustainability of the natural resource base, is not the only dimension of sustainability that is important to DFID. However, it is a major concern that it is not adequately captured in the other livelihood outcome categories. Although often viewed as a donor objective, it is shared by many who recognize long-term benefits of reasonable and careful use of resource.

One of the main difficulties in this part of the framework is that livelihood outcomes are not necessarily coherent and they are certainly incommensurable. It is hard to weigh up the relative value of increased well-being as opposed to increased income, but this is the type of decision that people must make every day when deciding which strategies to adopt (DFID, 2001).

Also, there would be a conflict between livelihood outcomes. An obvious example is when increased income for particular groups is achieved through practices that are detrimental to the natural resource base. Or perhaps different family members prioritize different livelihood objectives – some seeking to reduce vulnerability, while

February 28, 2021

others are seeking to maximize income streams. The framework does not offer any answers to these dilemmas, but does provide a structure for thinking them through, considering how they affect other aspects of livelihoods (e.g. strategies adopted) and perhaps coming to a mutually acceptable “solution” (DFID, 2001).

Laws, mechanisms and policies reflect the Party's and the State's leadership. The rule of law and policy are a compulsory element that all people must abide by and ethnic minorities are no exception. Wherever you are, what you do, everyone must respect and comply with the law, go with the Party's leadership. As a result, laws and policies are placed on the top of the sustainable livelihood analysis framework. Policy environment has a great impact and impact on the livelihoods of households in general and ethnic minority households in particular.

Often, a good and stable policy will provide more favorable conditions for farmers to implement their livelihood strategies. In contrast, a bad, unstable policy will cause difficulties, even directly affect their livelihood. Institutions and policies have a strong influence on ethnic minority people. Institutions and processes of policies affect all aspects of EM livelihood activities, creating incentives for ethnic minority people to make better choices.

Ethnic minority people have access to policies on infrastructure, education, health, preferential credit, new breeds, scientific and technical information, market information, and housing. Harmonization of policies and programs will contribute to the impacts of EMs and livelihood outcomes of ethnic minority people.

These are external factors that ethnic minority households do not or cannot intervene and control. These factors can have a major impact on the livelihood, employment and income of farmers. Those external factors can be

(i) Natural characteristics and disasters

Natural disasters such as extreme weather, extreme flooding, epidemics or erratic weather can be fatal to human life. Coping with environmental vulnerabilities, natural disasters and natural hazards is not a simple matter.

Some other characteristics such as the high humidity, climate and climate make it possible to develop wet rice farming, increase crops, and diversify crops and livestock. It also creates favorable conditions for the development of other economic sectors (forestry, fisheries, transport, tourism ...). However, the irregularity of weather and climate factors leading to many difficulties (natural disasters, epidemics ...)

(ii) Seasonality

For agricultural production, seasonality may affect productivity, yield production efficiency and labor use then effect to income of house hold

Seasonality can also affect to off farm job. The majority of seasonal migrants are employed in cultivation and plantations, brick-kilns, quarries, construction sites and fish processing. Further, large numbers of seasonal migrants work in urban informal manufacturing, construction, services or transport sectors, employed as casual laborers, head-loaders, rickshaw pullers and hawkers (Dev, 2002).

However, official awareness of the magnitude of seasonal migration or the importance of it in the lives of the poor is abysmally low. Policy-makers have tended to perceive migration largely as a problem, posing a threat to social and economic stability and have therefore tried to control it, rather than viewing it as an important livelihood option for the poor (Daniel Start, 2003).

(iii) Market

Price and market factors affect not only agricultural production households, but also the production, trade and service households. In short, external factors include both positive and negative factors.

February 28, 2021

Market accessibility could be considered as one of the most important factors affecting rural food security. It is often linked with various other stakeholders like processors, traders, and retailers (Birthal, Joshi PK, 2007). Being producers and consumers at the same time, market access plays two-way function for rural households. On one hand, they use the market to buy inputs or to sell farm produce. On the other hand, they use it to buy food and non-food items in order to sustain their living standards (IFAD, 2013). Market access may be hindered due to long distances from farm to market, transportation cost and market information (Ahmed UI, et al., 2016). Hence, better infrastructure and easy market access can play an important role in sustaining local food security through reduced transportation cost and food prices (Minten B, 1999). Market access could be defined in various ways like using proxies such as travel time, distance and cost (Baltenweck and Staal, 2007). In addition to market access, access to other institutional services, such as extension and credit are also important to enhance local access and utilization of food (Tembo and Simtwe, 2009).

Competition in quality and price of different types of agricultural commodities or price fluctuations in the market are also market factors affect to livelihood outcome.

(iv) Other factors: technical costs, unstable elements of the country's political situation.

Therefore, it is necessary to identify which factors are positive, and which are negative for orientation and measure to limit negative impacts of negative factors on livelihoods of ethnic minority households by taking advantage of opportunities that positive elements bring to their livelihoods.

Education has been identified as an important factor for achieving development (McKeown, Hopkins, Rizzi, & Chrystalbridge, 2002). Sen (1997) considers education as a means to enhance human capital, which makes a person more efficient in commodity production (Sen, 1997). Without education, developmental goals cannot be achieved (UNESCO, 2005). When considering livelihoods, employment and employability is a fundamental issue. However, finding a job is mainly determined by education (Chambers, 1997). Many researchers have shown that education is supposed to prepare people for jobs; with relevant knowledge, skills and capabilities, which will help people in general as minority people handle or step out of poverty (Lawrence, 2009).

Through education, people can achieve social equity and sustainable livelihoods and enhance their problem-solving ability (Hopkins and McKeown, 2002).

Cultural characteristics of ethnic minority people have a positive impact as well as negative impact on the livelihood of the people. The characteristics of indigenous knowledge in human capital can have a positive impact on the financial resources of ethnic minorities and the value of natural resources.

However, characteristics, such as production habits, superstitions and language barriers in human resources may also be factors that impede access and effective use. The financial resources and natural resources of ethnic minority people is an important characteristic of ethnic minorities in Viet Nam for their alternation (Mac Duong, 2005; Bui Minh Dao, 2011).

Most ethnic minority communes have two or more ethnic groups, with each village having a dominant ethnic group. Therefore, it is difficult to find the common denominator for all villages in the same commune. Even the same people, but living in different villages and living in different areas also have different characteristics to adapt to living conditions. For example, in the aspect of customary law, Ngo Duc Thinh (2010) and Bui Minh Dao (2013) point out that there is no customary law for a whole nation, whether majority or minority. It is customary for each village (Ngo Duc Thinh, 2010).

- Capacity of ethnic minorities: Ethnic minorities themselves have a low educational level, lack of scientific knowledge, lack of experience and often passive in their creative work. Capacity for livelihood activities and creation of livelihood assets are so limited. Therefore, the need to improve capacity of the people should be facilitated by their abilities to overcome shortcomings in various forms and appropriate measures.

February 28, 2021

Thus, Vietnamese villages, whether it is Kinh or ethnic minorities, have distinct characteristics. This suggests that interventions to improve livelihoods need to be tailored to each village. Each project must carefully survey each village in all aspects, promoting positive subjectivity of people and communities when designing and implementing specific activities.

In case of water availability in such a highland area, where most ethnic minorities are settled, is a crucial factor to improve agriculture productivity. Water itself could be utilized as crop cultivation, once irrigation channels or ponds by water harvest and small reservoir constructed by villager's level or by support from local government agencies.

Proper water availability is a key factor to improve their productivity in agriculture and livestock. This water facility such as irrigation could lead to better income, so that their livelihoods assets will be developed, naturally followed by livelihood improvement. While irrigation brings improved agricultural productivity, EM's health conditions will also improve through fresh non-contaminated water for drinking and cooking in their living. Use of clean and safe water shall bring healthy human capital, which would bring better productivity managing other four livelihood capitals as well.

Since the Renovation, development programs and projects of developed countries and non-governmental organizations have supported Vietnam. Most of them aim to improve the condition for vulnerable groups, such as rural people, ethnic minorities, and poor regions. These programs have made a positive contribution. They helped improving people's livelihoods, creating jobs, raising capacity, and giving autonomy capacity of community. These programs also have provided financial supports to improve infrastructure.

2.2. Main characteristics of livelihood of ethnic minority households

Firstly, livelihood assets of ethnic minorities are often very limited

Regarding human resources, due to low living standard, educational level and difficult access to family planning services, ethnic minorities often have many children with high population in one household. This form of high population household is advantageous to develop production, cultivation, husbandry, or crops that require much labor and working time.

However, it is also a great challenge to create jobs for ethnic minorities. The education and professional levels of ethnic minorities are often not quite high because of difficulties in accessing educational and vocational training. In addition, agricultural practices and resource developments for their livelihoods in the village prevent them from doing new jobs. Therefore, low level of education and profession become a big obstacle to the application of new science and advanced technology in order to intensify their productivity, product quality and production scale for livelihood improvement of ethnic minorities.

Income inequality can be solved in a short time, but inequality in human capital can lead to serious consequences over many generations. Therefore, investment in human capital is critical to break the vicious circle of poverty. The poor are poor because they lack human capital and the poor lack human capital because they are poor (McGillivray, 1991; Srinivasan, 1994). The poor are less educated, and a relationship between poverty and education is more striking, especially among ethnic minority women. Thus, raising human capital for the poor is considered as a key to getting rid of the vicious circle of poverty (Krantz, 2001).

In general, the human capital is a core value, it has a direct impact on exploitation of other resources for doing livelihood activities. Even in some cases, it acts as a substitute for other resources because of resource deficit. Natural resources of ethnic minorities include production land, forestland, water resources for production and consumption. The natural resources of ethnic minorities play a significant role, which is a basis for all of their livelihood activities. Natural resources are potential of ethnic minorities (Leite et al., 1999). If those resources

February 28, 2021

are developed and used well by ethnic minorities, they will contribute to positive effects on their sustainable livelihoods.

Regarding social resources: Social resources are used to help people pursue their livelihood goals, including relationships, networks, team members, beliefs, interdependence, and exchange of important informal security networks (Portes, 1995). Information dissemination in the ethnic minority community and households plays an important role in raising their social capital. If information is provided for households in a right way and timely manner, it will help households to increase their understanding in production, market trends and social understanding, raise their confidence and then to improve production efficiency. The local customs and practices are also social factors that affect the production and life of ethnic minorities (Eade, 1997). Family relations and neighborhood relations have a great influence on decision-making in the production process. Households often consult with many people before making decisions in production as well as livelihoods. The rich social resource with human identity is one of favorable factors to exploit and promote human resources and natural resources (Conte et al., 2002).

Material resources: Assets of ethnic minority communities are often considered as basic facilities for production and daily life such as electricity, roads, schools, health stations, irrigation system, water supply works, cultural houses, sports and communication works, local industrial parks, processing plants and production services (Liao et al., 2011).

The material assets of ethnic minority households include assets used for production and daily life such as land, machinery, animal reproduction and traction, production tools, housing, means of transportation, living facilities of the household. Material capitals have great influence on employment, production development, income and livelihood of the ethnic minority community and households (Morrow, 1999; Sunderlin et al., 2005). However, it is also one of the factors that restrain household's livelihood from improvement due to the shortage and inconsistency of infrastructure, the lack of investment capital of the community and household. Well-invested material resources will have a great impact promoting potentials of human resources, natural resources, social and financial resources (Leigh et al., 2016).

Financial resources: Financial resources are determined by employment and income of household members. The financial difficulties lead to a reduction of possibility in household economic development. Thus, in order to improve the household economy, it is very essential to develop financial resources for investment in production scale, productivity and product quality (Tri et al., 2002). Assistance of loans to ethnic minorities is becoming an important source of finance for the production development of each household. Improved financial resources will be a solid economic factor for enhancing human capacity, increasing material resources, improving natural and social resources, and exploiting them effectively in livelihood activities (Smith et al., 2005).

Secondly, ethnic minorities often live in mountainous and difficult areas, so they have low income, monotonous production activities, low employment opportunities and unsustainable livelihoods (Boothroyd et al., 2000; Baulch, 2010).

Thirdly, ethnic minority households are often exposed to major risks, especially from natural disasters and weather. Because they live in mountainous and difficult areas, they are more likely to be at risk (Wisner et al., 1993; Blaikie et al., 2014). Moreover, due to difficult transportation, they also face many risks of market, especially in agricultural product consumption (Van de Walle, 1998; Manuta et al., 2005; Fischer et al., 2010; Thomas et al., 2010).

Fourthly, the culture identity, property, indigenous knowledge of ethnic minorities is preserved. The traditional culture of ethnic minorities is the material and spiritual values that are accumulated and preserved throughout the history of ethnic minority development (Yosso, 2005). Under the context of globalization, preservation of

February 28, 2021

ethnic minority culture is aimed at maintaining the diversity of Vietnamese culture, enriching the world's cultural treasures (Taylor, 2008). It helps increase the exploitation of cultural resources and boost the country's economic development. Besides, culture preservation contributes to raising the nation's pride and self-respect and struggling against hostile forces. However, in the current context of modern life, together with an opportunity of exchange and integration, there is a risk of losing many traditional cultural values, especially culture of ethnic minorities. Therefore, preservation and promotion of ethnic minority culture is an urgent task for sustainable development of the country (Seabrook, 2004). In order to do so, one of the basic solutions is to improve the living standards of ethnic minorities through livelihood improvement (Kofinas et al., 2009).

2.3. Research on livelihood improvement of ethnic minority households

A study by Dinh Duc Thuan (2005) was on "Forestry, Poverty Reduction and Rural Livelihoods in Vietnam". The objective of the study was to provide specific recommendations for the policy-making process, so that forests and forest products can sustainably contribute to forest-dependent people in Vietnam (Dinh Duc Thuan, 2005).

The topic clearly indicates that the majority of household groups in the development of livelihood strategies emphasize the importance of raising awareness and developing human resources in the future. Improvements in infrastructure, such as roads, electricity networks, irrigation system, schools, health care, and information systems are strategic solutions that are interests of all groups of households.

However, for each group of households, there are also specific livelihood strategies that poor households prioritize; food security, breeding and technical support for production, preferential loans for investment on livestock, medical assistance, medicines. Group of new households escaping from poverty prioritize for upgrading agro-forestry techniques, diversifying income sources, reforming administrative procedures in production and circulation of goods.

Preferably households choose to diversify their sources of income, including non-farm jobs, investments in children's education, and exchange of experiences. The study of Nguyen Quoc Nghi and Bui Van Trinh (2011) was on "Factors affecting income of ethnic minorities in the Mekong Delta" in Journal of Science.

By analyzing the real situation of resources, the lives of the Cham and the Khmer in the Mekong Delta show that, besides the abundant natural resources and rich social resources of the ethnic minority people, financial and human resources are still limited. Level of education and production capital is low. In addition to some households with sufficient material life, many ethnic minority households are facing difficulties due to the lack of daily necessities and public services (Nguyen Quoc Nghi et al., 2014).

The factors influencing the monthly income of the Cham and Khmer are the educational level of the household head, household labor, household size, income generation activity, age of household labor and access to supportive policies. The research has proposed groups of solutions that will contribute to generate income for ethnic minority people.

In addition, the authors expect that the concerned organizations and individuals will study and implement to increase income and improve their living standards of ethnic minorities in the Mekong Delta. The study by Tran Tien Khai and Nguyen Ngoc Danh (2012) on "The relationship between livelihoods and rural poverty in Vietnam", explores an interrelationship between livelihood assets and poverty of rural households in Vietnam.

The study indicates that multidimensional rural poverty can be identified based on a number of socio-economic indicators and household livelihood assets. Multidimensional poverty has at least ten dimensions that represent the four groups of human capitals, physical, financial and household.

February 28, 2021

Human resources are represented by three independent dimensions: human resources for agriculture, health and employment diversification. Physical capitals measured in five dimensions are housing status, residential comfort, production assets, common consumer assets and luxury consumer goods.

The area of agricultural land represents the natural resource and the secondary income represents the financial resources. In other words, the concept of multi-dimensional poverty in rural Vietnam can be interpreted with ten different socio-economic dimensions.

Oxfam and Action aid (2013) study on "Poverty Reduction Models in Some Ethnic Communities in Viet Nam: A Case Study in Ha Giang, Nghe An and Dak Nong". The study uses a bright spot approach in the analysis of "poverty alleviation models" to understand the factors that lead to typical ethnic minority households and communities that have a better poverty reduction and better life outcome. Households and other communities are in the same context. The results show that "poverty reduction models" in mountainous and ethnic minority areas are characterized by distinct villages (Sunderlin et al., 2005).

There is no ideal "poverty reduction model". "Poverty alleviation models" are always self-motivated in the context of rapid change. The essence of "scaling up the poverty reduction model" is to replicate the approach; it is a methodology and process-based model based on cultural diversity and the positive of the people, without further analyzing the livelihoods of the farmers.

A study by the World Bank and the Ministry of Planning and Investment (2013) was on the "Socio-economic Impact Assessment Report for the Central Highlands Poverty Reduction Project". The Central Highlands Poverty Reduction Project aims to improve livelihood opportunities for poor households and communities in 26 districts in the six project provinces (World Bank, 2013). The project beneficiaries are poor households, in which the poor are ethnic minority people and vulnerable women who receive special attention from the project.

In the study, poverty is aggregated into two main categories: (1) an access to livelihood capital sources; (2) adverse contexts that increase vulnerability of target groups. The assessment shows that vulnerable groups are the poor group in general, in which the ethnic minority groups are resettled on the spot, ethnic minorities migrate freely within 5 years and the patriarchal group and matrices.

The assessment shows that the need for livelihood development is to reach the target groups. Disadvantaged groups are more disadvantaged than Kinh groups in the project area; the female-headed households are more disadvantaged than the male-headed ones.

Land resources, in terms of area, are not detrimental to the ethnic minority groups in place due to the accumulation of land from the fatherland, but the use of land efficiency of this group is less favorable than Kinh and ethnic minorities migrate, but the study has not analyzed the EM population.

Solutions to improve income for ethnic minority communities are also of interests to authors, with a variety of approaches (Hoang Hoe, 1998; Nguyen Thi Nguyet, 2002; Vu Van Thinh, 2014). The major income-generating solutions are the development of agricultural production for buffer zone communities.

The results of the study by Le Dien Duc (2002), Nguyen Thi Phuong (2003), all agreed that to sustain life, ethnic minorities households living around the reserve are forced to exploit natural resources and create pressures for biodiversity conservation, and there is a need for effective solutions to improve living standards of people, especially for poor people, and to raise awareness of natural resources protection at the same time (Le Dien Duc, 2002).

3. Conclusion

February 28, 2021

Case studies show that there are no ideal livelihood models, but models are often adapted to the context of ongoing economic development. Therefore, improving livelihoods for ethnic minorities to adapt to change is necessary. Lessons learned from the practice are:

Firstly, it is necessary to focus on improving the education and skills of ethnic minorities by expanding the network of schools and developing vocational training for ethnic minorities.

In addition, it is necessary to have policies to support production establishments, cooperative economic organizations, enterprises and farm owners to effectively operate in their community, to facilitate the application. This creates more jobs and opportunities for ethnic minorities to adopt preferential policies for units employing many ethnic minorities.

Secondly, access to financial resources for ethnic minorities needs to be improved through diversification of forms of credit support for them, with particular emphasis on supporting projects of foreigners for ethnic minorities.

Thirdly, attention should be paid to "linking communities" in "livelihoods" to increase livelihood efficiency, spillover and sustain new practices. Maintaining and developing social relationships that help improving the social capital of ethnic minorities is their fulcrum when facing difficulties.

Fourthly, it is necessary to take advantage of each village to increase its ability to adapt to new conditions. Ethnic minority livelihood strategies will be more successful when based on the advantages of geographical location, natural conditions, and infrastructure. Traditional handicrafts and specialties, social relations, mobilized cash flows of each village can be considered.

Fifth, it is necessary to strengthen risk prevention capacity of the people and ethnic minority communities. This is a shortcoming, adversely affecting the sustainability of "livelihood models".

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